

conCEPTION

SAFETY EVIDENCE ECOSYSTEM

Everything you want to know about medicine use during pregnancy.
Share your experiences!

What is Moeders van Morgen?

Moeders van Morgen collects information on your experiences as a (future) mother through online questionnaires. We ask questions about your health, lifestyle, and whether or not you use medicines during your pregnancy. Medicines also include over-the-counter products, vaccinations, folic acid and vitamins.

Why would you participate?

With your participation, you can help the future mothers. You can share valuable information about your experiences before, during and after pregnancy. This information provides insight into choices made during pregnancy. Therefore, we can improve the information we provide to healthcare providers and women!

Do you have questions about medicine use during pregnancy?

We understand you may have questions about the use of medicines before, during and after pregnancy. Evidence-based information can be found on the website www.moedersvanmorgen.nl/kennisbank. Discuss your medicine use always with your midwife, gynecologist and/or your physician. Consult always a specialist when you want to stop or start any kind of medicine.

Subscribing

You can participate in the study through our website www.moedersvanmorgen.nl. Here you can find more information

Or you can contact us by e-mail: info@moedersvanmorgen.nl or telephone: 073- 64 69 700.

When can you subscribe and what's next?

You can participate in the study at any point during your pregnancy, but preferably as early in the pregnancy as possible. Immediately after entering into the study, you will receive the first online questionnaire, the second questionnaire will be administered around the 17th week of gestation and the third questionnaire around 34 weeks of gestation. You will receive questionnaires 4, 5 and 6, approximately 2, 6, and 12 months postpartum.

Administering the first questionnaires will take around 10 to 30 minutes, due to its extensiveness. Administering additional questionnaires will take around 5 to 20 minutes.

About 'Moeders van Morgen'

Moeders van Morgen is the Dutch National Institute for medicine use among women with a wish to conceive, pregnant women and women who breastfeed. Moeders van Morgen is part of the Netherlands Pharmacovigilance Centre Lareb. We gain knowledge through our research, but we also present information about the safety of medicine use within our online knowledge bank.